

STS and Citizen Science Colloquium

2 April 2024

Visual Mapping

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Canvas 1: Where do we stand?
How do you position yourself?

Canvas 2: Engagement and Reflexivity
How do you position yourself?

Canvas 3: Group discussions
How do you position yourself?

Canvas 4: How is STS made & done in CS and vice versa?

